

SECOND BHAVA ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

Second bhava is very important for material life. In this earth we all want to live comfortable. Everyman wants to earn money till his death. There are some ways to find out our wealth condition in astrology through fortuna and indu lagna. Dhana yogas point out our wealth status.

Key Words: Planets - Karagas Dhanayoga Sun in Second bhava - Moon in Second bhava - Mars in Second bhava - Mercury Jupiter in Second bhava - Venus in Second bhava - Saturn in Second bhava - Rahu in Second bhava - Kethu in Second bhava - Manthi in Second bhava - Kuligan in Second bhava - Aries as second bhava - Taurus as Second bhava - Gemini as Second bhava - Cancer as Second bhava - Leo as Second bhava - Virgo as Second bhava - Libra as Second bhava - Scorpio as Second bhava - Sagittarius as Second bhava - Capricorn as Second bhava - Aquaris as Second bhava - Pisces as Second bhava.

Introduction:

Money is essential for human life. In astrology Second bhava indicates one's wealth condition. The second bhava is called dhana sthana, vakku (words) sthana, family sthana, nethra (eye) sthana and taste (rushi) sthana. Jupiter is the planet for wealth. The Second bhava lord and Jupiter decide one's wealth. 2/5/8/11 bhavas are called panaparasthana (Dhana kendra). 2/6/10 bhavas are called karma trine. We can calculate one's wealth by seeing the weightage of the above bhavas.

Planets and Their Related Karagas:

- Sun: Sun is the athma karaga. The followings are the karagas of the Sun. Father, Eyes, Light, Fire, Shiva, Government support, Taste, Bone, King, Administration, Kumkum, Time management, Punctuality and Best quality.
- Moon: The followings are the karagas of the Moon. Mother, Flower, Scent, Silver, Travels, Well, Pearl, Sugarcane, Face attraction, White colour, Milk, Curd, Crystal and Salt.
- Mars: The followings are the karagas of the Mars. Earth, Younger Brother, Bravery, Weapons, War, Enemy, Fool, Tension, Anger, Fear, Fire, Argument, Heat, Hammer, Meat eating.
- Mercury: The followings are the karagas of the Mercury. Education, Calculation, Astrology, Green, Sculpture, Temple, Business, Veda, Bad dream, Bronze, Child, Dance, Comedy Sense, Maternal Uncle, Communication, Mass media, TV and Computer.
- Venus: The followings are the karagas of the Venus. Beauty, Attraction, Love, Black money, Silver, Sexual happiness, Harmones, Illegal contacts, Make up, Wife, Alcohol, and Diamond.
- Saturn: The followings are the karagas of the Saturn. Lazy, Aged person, Disabled challenged persons, Life span, Labours, Black colour, Pain, Poverty, Infertility, Night duty, Paralysis, Loss and Blue sapphire.
- Rahu: The followings are the karagas of the Rahu. Spleen, Grandfather, Cold, Foreign travel, Filthy words, Arguments, Devil, Mandrigam, Foreign religions, Photo, Cinema, X-ray, Xerox, Prison, Export, Import, Cancer and Gomed.
- Kethu: The followings are the karagas of the Kethu. Poison, Drugs, Rebel, Bomb, Crackers, Wisdom, Divorce, Ganesh, Asthma, Dog, Cock and Cat's eye.

Planets in Second Bhava:

- Sun in second bhava: If Sun stands in second bhava the native is liked by the king. He/she has eye diseases. They act against their child. Their friends become as their enemies. They earn money in many ways. They have knowledge in astrology.
- Moon in Second bhava: Moon stands in second bhava the native should learn many arts. He/she gets marriage at young age. He/she speaks sweet words. They are wealthy people. They have good friends. They have eye disease. They are very interested in sex. They have good children.
- Mars in second bhava: They are very dangerous. They earn enemies by their speech. They suffer by constipation. They should worry in land matters.

- Mercury in Second bhava: They are interested in education. They speak sweet words. They have good personality. They have face attraction. They have social status. They earn money by law and astrology.
- Jupiter in second bhava: They are equal to king. They are educationalist. They get marriage in earlier age. They are spiritualist. They respect elders. They have leadership quality. They eat tasty food.
- Venus in Second bhava: They are liked by everyone. They always criticize others. They get marriage in earlier age. They are very much interested in intercourse. They donate money very well. They eat tasty food. They speak sweet words.
- Saturn in Second bhava: They have more than one spouse. They earn enemies by their speech. They are lazy, and do everything very slowly. They have teeth disease. They enjoy other's wealth.
- Rahu in Second bhava: They have always worries. They are poor. They speak filthy words. They earn enemies by their speech. They eat bad food. They have disease in eye and teeth.
- Kethu in Second bhava: They are enemies to their relatives. They speak poisonous words. They know many things. They earn money by cheat others.
- Kuligan in second bhava: They have eye disease. They speak unworthy words. They always waste their money. They earn enemies by their speech.
- Manthi in second bhava: They always argue with others. They are always with tension. They have eye disease.

Dhana Yogam:

- Second lord and fifth lord exchange makes one a wealthy person.
- Second lord and eleventh lord exchange makes one a wealthy person.
- Jupiter conjunctions with mercury makes one a wealthy person.
- Jupiter conjunctions with second lord makes one a wealthy person.
- Second lord stands in lagna makes one a wealthy person.

12 Signs and Second Bhavas:

- Aries: Taurus is second bhava for Aries. So, Aries people earn and enjoy money through arts, cinema, fancy stores and textiles.
- Taurus: Gemini is the second bhava for taurus. So, Taurus people earn and enjoy money through their speech as lawyer or astrologer. Commission agent business also helps them.
- Gemini: Cancer is the second bhava for Gemini. So, Gemini people earn and enjoy money through travels, hotels, nursing, teaching and by agriculture.
- Cancer: Leo is the second bhava for cancer. So, cancer people earn and enjoy money through doing government contracts, tenders, with the help of father and politicians.
- Leo: Virgo is the second bhava for Leo. So, Leo people earn and enjoy money through
- Virgo: Libra is the second bhava for virgo so, virgo people earn and enjoy money through arts, cinema, fancy stores and textiles.
- Libra: Scorpio is the second bhava for Libra. So, Libra people earn and enjoy money through uniform jobs like police, army fire rescue etc... They also earn money through rowdyism.
- Scorpio: Sagittarius is the second bhava for Scorpio. So, Scorpio people earn and enjoy money through teaching, Banking jobs and work as priest, giving advice and counselling to others.
- Sagittarius: Capricorn is the second bhava for sagittarius. So, sagittarius people earn and enjoy money through iron related business, drainage and waste material business, doing physical labour works.
- Capricorn: Aquaris is the second bhava for capricorn. So, capricorn people earn and enjoy money through arts, cinema, fancy stores and textiles.
- Aquaris: Pisces is the second bhava for Aquaris. So, Aquaris people earn and enjoy through teaching, Banking jobs and work as priest, giving advice and counselling to others.
- Pisces: Aries is the second bhava for pisces. So, pisces people earn and enjoy through uniform jobs like police, army fire rescue etc... They also earn money through rowdyism.

Conclusion:

Understand the way of income is very important. Astrology helps us to know the way of income. If we do our work or job according to astrology, our financial status will be sound.

References:

1. Varaga hora sasthanam Written by Adigalasiriyar published by Saraswathi Mahal Library, Tanjore.
2. Jothida Kelvigalum Sutchuma Pathilgalum written by Abirami K. Sekar published by Auromirra publications.
3. Thuyya Keralam written by Isakki published by Lotus publications house.
4. Ilakkiyathil Melanmai written by Iraianbu IAS published by New century book house chennai.
5. Jothida chakkarangalum Palan kanum Muraigalum written by Ettayapuram vijaya Narasimman published by Sri Auromirra publications.

6. Sarva Jathaga santhega Nivarthi written by Ekambara Mudaliyar published by Sridevi Puthaga Nilayam, Chennai.
7. Sitrilakkiyangalil Jothidam written by Dr. A. Ganesan published by Ramiah Pathipagam, Chennai.
8. Varka Chakkarangalum Palan Koorum Muraigalum written by Dr. A. Ganesan published by Sri Auomira publications.
9. Jathaga Chandrigai written by Krishna moorthy sastrigal published by Saraswathi Mahal Library, Tanjore.
10. Uthira Kalamirtham written by Mahakavi Kalidasar Translated by Kumaraswamy Achari published by Sri Anandha Nilayam, Chennai.
11. Saravali written by Kalyana Varma Translated by Kumara swamy Achari published by Sri Anandha Nilayam, Chennai.
12. Kumara swamiyam written by Kumaraswamy Desikar published by Rockfort publications, Chennai.
13. Uthrakalamirtham written by Mahakavi alidasar Translated by Ettayapuram Gopikrishnan published by Kumaran Pathipagam, Chennai.
14. Sathaga Alangaram written by Keeranur Natarajan explained by C. Govindarasanar published by Saraswathi Mahal Library, Tanjore.
15. Kumara swamiyam written by Kumaraswamy Desikar, explained by Sathyabama Kameswaran published by Saraswathi Mahal Library, Tanjore.